

**THE IMPACT OF THE ADVENT OF GENERATION Z ON
INTERGENERATIONAL RELATIONS IN MOROCCAN PUBLIC
ESTABLISHMENTS: CASE OF THE MOROCCAN AVIATION AUTHORITIES
(OFFICE NATIONAL DES AEROPORTS (ONDA)).**

Mohamed Faik: PhD student , Hassan First University of Settat, ENCG Settat , LRMMC, Morocco

Abdelkabar AIT MARIM: PhD student , Hassan II University, Casablanca city, Morocco

Madame SOUAD Rafiq: Teacher-researcher Hassan First University of Settat, ENCG Settat ,
LRMMC, Morocco

Madame Mina Makboul: University professor, Hassan II University, Casablanca city, Morocco

ABSTRACT

Generation Z is changing the worlds of work and management. Autonomous, focused on innovation and demanding . They require companies to be more flexible and above all open to its various partners.

What is the impact of the advent of Generation Z on intergenerational relationships in the company? Finding an answer to this question requires studying the cohabitation of three generations in the business world: baby boomers, generation X and generation Y. They will soon be four, with the imminent arrival of generation Z in the labor market. However, each has its own characteristics , expectations and perception of work. Each company must reconcile the 3 generations at work in order to benefit from the strengths of each. It must therefore make Generation Z the talents of today, and the leaders of tomorrow, while reconciling the expectations of Generations X, Y and seniors at the end of their careers. For this, the company must quickly adapt its management policy, in order to achieve generational diversity.

Keywords :

generation Z ; intergenerational relationships ; cohabitation ; labor market; perception of work ; talents ; management ; generational diversity.

Résumé

La génération Z est en train de bouleverser les mondes de travail et de management. Autonomes, portée sur l'innovation et exigeants. La génération Z pousse l'entreprise à être flexible et surtout ouverte sur ses différents partenaires.

Quel est l'impact de l'avènement de la génération Z sur les relations intergénérationnelles dans l'entreprise ? Chercher une réponse à cette question nécessite d'étudier la cohabitation de trois générations dans le monde de l'entreprise : les baby-boomers, la génération X et la génération Y. Elles seront bientôt quatre, avec l'arrivée imminente de la génération Z sur le marché du travail. Or, chacune a ses propres particularités, ses attentes et sa perception de travail. Chaque entreprise se doit de concilier les 3 générations au travail afin de profiter des forces de chacune. Elle lui faut donc faire de la génération Z les talents d'aujourd'hui, et les leaders de demain, tout en conciliant les attentes des générations X, Y et des séniors en fin de carrière. Pour cela, l'entreprise se doit d'adapter rapidement sa politique de management, afin de réussir la diversité générationnelle.

Mots clés : *Génération Z ; relations intergénérationnelles ; cohabitation ; le marché du travail ; perception de travail ; talents ; management ; diversité générationnelle .*

Study context

The issue of generational conflict within a company is complex. It raises both conceptual and methodological difficulties, relating to the measurement of inequalities between generations and the choice of indicators but also to the definition of what is considered unfair, which refers to the underlying principles of justice that it is important to clarify. Generational conflict can be fueled by the fact that some generations feel aggrieved and think, for example, that this is the result of deliberate policy. Conflicts between generations date from the dawn of time. In addition to the usual differences, there is the relationship to the technology that has developed so rapidly over the past decades,

The idea of generational conflict, asserted on both sides in different forms, is based on the construction of groups constituting each generation, with a series of characteristics. Some would be disrespectful, individualistic and ambitious at the expense of the quality of work while others would only be concerned with maintaining their benchmarks, their internal rules, preventing any possibility of evolution of forms of work in the name of tradition and experience-based authority.

On the other hand, Conflicts affect business productivity. Indeed, in a commercial establishment, the relationships between young and old can illustrate the level of debate that we have regularly observed. These debates focus on behavior at work and the criteria for defining the quality of relationships. The elders assert their attachment to the traditional spirit of business and to collective solidarity. They deplore the "individualism of young people" who do not fit into this system of relationships. For their part, young people affirm their attachment to the quality of relationships at work and in particular to the importance of the atmosphere, but refuse to enter into forms of socialization outside working time that the elders suggest to them. A good way to reduce these conflicts originating from generational differences is to integrate them into the company. Understanding who we are and who the other is the basis for better collaboration. Then, use those differences in mutual assistance and collaboration.

This item deals with conflicts that can arise between different generations, due to their differences, within the company. We will first treat the notion of generation, then determine the types and different characteristics of these generations, to achieve, the advent of Generation Z and its impact on intergenerational relations within companies.

The theoretical part try to demonstrate that the differences in cultures, environment and lifestyles of these generations induce conflicts that can have a negative impact on the company. The empirical part will be used to determine if this also applies to the Moroccan context by trying to discuss generational diversity in a company operating in the aeronautical field, in particular the Moroccan Aviation Authorities (Office National Des Aéroports (ONDA)).

1. Theoretical framework of generation.

The concept of generation is a transdisciplinary notion resulting from the human and social science, whose most-used approach in management science, the generational cohort, has its roots in the theory of socialization (Ward, 1974) ", this term mainly designates a generation (or group of individuals) having similar experiences at a given moment, having grown up in an environment with specific codes and practices .

1.1. Definition of the generation concept.

The literature on the subject is old and abundant. "In democracies, each generation is a new people"¹ said Alexis Deoqueville in the 19th century.

The notion of "generation" belongs to a multitude of scientific dimensions: psychology, psychoanalysis, anthropology, history, political science and of course sociology. As many disciplines as there are connotations and even ambiguities according to Gérard MAUGER². The Littré dictionary distinguishes two uses, one applied to family lineage and filiation, the other to a temporality of individuals "living at the same time or more or less", in particular to a society. For the Civil Code, a family generation represents a degree of filiation³.

During the 19th and early 20th century, the generation represents a historical measuring instrument of time. Then from the 1950s, the notion of generation tends to diversify through several approaches. For a demographer, it is a question of taking into account all the individuals of the same year, for a historian it represents the duration of renewal of the men of public life, for a genealogist it is a relation of filiation . The biological notion is therefore a first approach to structuring individuals according to their age and social status. For Olivier GALLAND⁴, "The transition to adulthood is the relevant level to differentiate between age groups." Age appears here as a complex social construct depending on the cultural model and the strategy of the company. If the passage to adulthood combined with rites of passage presents an obvious evolution, does it represent the distinction of one generation from another?

¹ DE TOCQUEVILLE Alexis, 1835, *De la Démocratie en Amérique, OEuvres II*, Paris, Gallimard, p. 566-572.

² MAUGER Gérard, 2009, *Génération et rapports de générations*, revue internationale de la philosophie, n°46, p. 109-126

³ Code civil français, article 741

⁴ GALLAND Olivier, 2011, *Sociologie de la jeunesse*, Armand Colin

According to sociologists, a new generation appears roughly every twenty years. The names given to these generations and years of birth of their members may vary according to the authors, but experts agree that four (4) major generations coexist today in the labor market.

Indeed, many authors distinguish four (4) generations by the following names: *baby boomers, generation X, generation Y and the last called generation Z.*

Since our issue focuses on the arrival of Generation Z on the labor market, we will focus, in this section, on the different characteristics of this generation as well as its impact on the company's organizational culture.

1.2. Generation Z: emergence, characteristics, expectations and behavior.

In contrary of millennials, the literature does not yet abound in favor of this generation of individuals born after 1995. Indeed not yet inserted in the professional environment, they are beginning to form this generation Z also called generation C for "communicative" or "native social media" in reference to tools such as smart phones, tablets and social media. As such, they are the true "digital natives" because, unlike the millennials, they all grew up with technology at their fingertips.

The concept of generation Z defines the segment of the population succeeding Y. The term originally comes from the generation theory created by William Strauss and Neil Howe. In their book *Generations* (1991), the two authors refer to a cycle of generational renewal. They were born in an information and communication technology environment. Globally, their expectations are close to those of millennials.

They will have no difficulty finding a job (Rioux, 2012). For this generation, the virtual world is a must (Rivard, 2011). Generation Z is also known as Generation Homeland, Gen I, Digital Generation (Igel and Urquhart, 2012). Allain (2008) calls them "Zapping" and "they come, for a large majority of them, from parents of Generation X, indulgent and permissive parents". Allain (2014) also refers to the anthropologist, "Wesch (2016) who calls them 'emos' (short for emotion), while Allain (2014) considers generation Z to include those born between 1995 and 2010. Williams, (2010) prefers to say that this generation begins in 1995, while the authors (Bennett, Pitt, and Price, 2012; Hernaus and PološkiVokic, 2014; Ozkan and Solmaz, 2015) consider the year 2000 as the starting point for generation Z. Pauget and Dammak(2015) generalize and determine that this 'generation begins since 1995 or 2001 depending on the sources'. Note that Mc Crindle and Wolfinger (2009) refer to the α (alpha) generation born around 2010.

1.3. Generation Z: new postures, new challenges for the company

The arrival of Generation Z in companies is calling into question the role of management. No more hierarchical authority and statutory power. In general, Zs have a hazy and distorted image of the company. The main problem of generation Zs is their complicated relationship with management. They can't stand hierarchy and overly supervised work. No more vertical organization for this generation, you will have to opt for a more horizontal organization of your resources. Their mistrust of authority is not absolute, but they will not respect you just because of your degree, your hierarchical superiority or your seniority in the company. Generation Z will first and foremost respect the entrepreneurial capacity of their management,

their ability to listen and inspire confidence. However, when a Z commits to a project, it is voluntary and militant. These young people have real expectations of their future company: it must be more human and flexible, with a flattened and more flexible hierarchy. Thus, employers will have to reassure newcomers, take the time to integrate them, and they will gain by taking a step back from their management model. The Zs are in another frame of reference where seniority does not make a person legitimate. Having easy access to knowledge, they can sometimes be considered arrogant by other generations, intergenerational clashes are possible. For the baby boomers (born between 1945 and 1975) and Generation X, this will be a real revolution.

According to a Didier Pitelet, Employer brand expert and CEO of Moon's Factory. The arrival of Generation Z poses three major challenges for the company:

First challenge: attractiveness. Didier Pitelet: "The aspirations of a young person in 2017? In order: to set up his own business, go to an SME, then to a large company (preferably unlisted), and finally to join the civil service. Or the exact opposite of what was observed 20 years ago. Will they become a generation of entrepreneurs? That remains to be seen, but one thing is certain: they will clearly be entrepreneurs for life. ».

Accustomed to change, they will leave their company if it is no longer in line with their values and the missions that interest them. Actors in their professional life, they need to control their career path in and out of the company.

Second challenge: management. Didier Pitelet: "The whole life of the Zs is in project mode, and they can only conceive of work with concrete and precise objectives, and regular feedback. Beyond that, it is also a

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

question of adapting to the pace of this generation, which has moved beyond the notion of work-life balance. They are constantly moving from one to the other. »

The annual interview disappears in favour of continuous feedback and collaborative management becomes the norm: brainstorming, trust, choice and responsibility are managerial values advocated by generations Y and Z. Giving responsibilities also means freeing creativity.

Third challenge: the quest for meaning. Didier Pitelet: "The Zs join the millennials in this need to understand: what are they for? And what is the purpose of the company?"

This is why the question of corporate culture is so central. Even if it is not politically correct, it seems to me that a company must be "culturally discriminatory". That is to say, clearly assert an identity and values, and therefore be able to say who will be able or not to flourish there? »

1.4 Generation Z and organizational culture:

The notion of "generation" is still the subject of opposition between authors, and this form of "Manichaeism" can be problematic. The majority of authors consider the arrival of the younger generations as the emergence of a new "intangible" and new reality to be taken into account. Others see it as the artifice of a reality constructed in marketing but which is not based on anything serious or sustainable (Pralong, 2008; Pichault and Pleyers, 2012).

According to (Jullien, 2009, 2016), "a culture does not have a definitive identity because it is constantly changing". Since the search for this identity is futile, we should therefore try to understand what underpins its existence: i.e. the permanent renewal and borrowing of new generational resources which might have been silent or even absent. Generations thus represent potential new resources that are being integrated, without interruption, into the world of work. The "noria effect" represented by this permanent contribution is therefore not in itself the arrival of a new identity, but the emergence of a new "dialogue" between the generations. For example, what some people took for granted (a successful career in the same company / generation X) is no longer a reliable fact (for generation Y, working life necessarily involves many changes of position in various companies).

Now, let's provide some elements of definition regarding organizational culture. "Culture is a set of fundamental beliefs and assumptions shared by the members of an organization. These assumptions operate unconsciously, and they have solved problems and are still solving them. Moreover, they must be transmitted to new people" (Schein, translated by Thévenet, 1986). The organizational culture would therefore make it possible to solve problems of external adaptation and internal integration. This point is essential because it is consistent with the project of this item, which is to identify the preferences of generation Z allowing their good adaptation to their external environment and their integration into the company. Schein's (1992) approach consists of describing corporate culture according to three components that are present concurrently and which are the artefacts, values and basic assumptions. The basic assumptions are fundamental beliefs about human nature and reality. Values represent principles that hold a truth, which best describe the beliefs of individuals within an organization.

Finally, artefacts are tangible results, observable translations of basic assumptions and values. Culture operate as an adaptive and regulatory system within the organization, whose function is to adapt to its environment.

The table below represents the fundamental characteristics of Generation Z according to the authors.

Table 1. Characteristics of generation Z

Proposed by author Dalmas (2018).

Characteristics of generation Z	Authors.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different modalities of trust from generation Y. Colleagues and direct superiors are more valued than the organization itself. • Criteria considered essential to the work : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Respect for people - Open and transparent communication - Communication based on the virtual - An ethical attitude towards people and the environment - Setting an example - Quality work 	<p>Www.ey.com Wood (2013) Iorgulescu (2016) Bencsik and Machova (2016)</p>

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaborative and cooperative work • Trust at work is based on : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The respect of commitments - Job security - Opportunities for advancement - Good pay conditions - Respect for diversity and equal treatment - An ethical approach to labor issues - Recognized as innovative and creative. • The values of life in general : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Living in the present - Seeking happiness with what we have A desire to feel safe A desire to escape even temporarily from the realities they face. 	
--	--

2. Presentation of the field of study

2.1. Presentation of ONDA :

The Moroccan National Airports Authority (ONDA) is a public establishment of an industrial and commercial nature created in January 1990 by the transformation of the Office of Airports of Casablanca, the first autonomous airport management establishment in Morocco.

The Office of Airports of Casablanca (OAC) was created in 1980 through Law 25-79 introducing the notion of airport management autonomy and the setting up of a company structure. In 1990, Law 14-89 ruled on its transformation into the National Airports Office. Decree 89-480 was then implemented for the application of this law.

Law 47-00 attached the training of air safety controllers and electronics engineers to this office. The ONDA has thus become the first autonomous public institution for airport management of an industrial nature.

Missions of ONDA:

As defined within the framework of laws 25-79, 14-89 and 47-00, the missions of the National Airports Office, a public establishment of an industrial and commercial nature endowed with legal personality and financial autonomy, reside essentially in providing the safety of air navigation at airports and in the airspace under national jurisdiction, and in the planning, operation, maintenance and development of the State's civil airports, the boarding, landing, transit of passengers, goods and mail carried by air, as well as all services designed to meet the needs of users and the public, relationship with international organizations and airports in order to meet the needs of air traffic, and the training of human resources such as air traffic controllers, engineers and air safety electronics engineers.

2.2. Division of labor within the ONDA

The test of the research model was carried out within a large Moroccan public company in the aviation sector, in this case the ONDA. Confronted with a double movement of ageing of its workforce and significant arrivals of young employees called Z in a context of teamwork, the management has to deal with generational diversity. A representative sample of the population in this establishment consisted of 2440 people whose characteristics are gathered in the table below :

Table.2: The distribution of the ONDA workforce according to generations

Génération	workforce	percentage
Baby boomers	318	13,03%
Génération X	786	32,21%
Génération Y	1203	49,30%
Génération Z	133	5,45%
Total	2440	100%

2.3 Methodology and data collection

2.3.1. Issues and methodology of the empirical study

At the end of our literature review, our issue is to see if the arrival of generation Z would impact intergenerational relations within the ONDA. A particular look will be taken at the integration and loyalty of generation Z.

Our challenge will be to answer the question: **Would the arrival of generation Z impact intergenerational relations within the ONDA?**

The qualitative research method seemed to be the most suitable for dealing with the problem of the item.

Our study was conducted in the form of semi-directive interviews. The collection of information through semi-structured interviews makes it possible to focus the discourse of the interviewees on the themes defined beforehand and recorded in an interview guide constructed in a uniform manner despite the diversity of the actors.

2.3.2. Process of the qualitative study

In order to achieve our research objectives, we adopted an exploratory qualitative approach based on the following three data collection methods: observation, documentary analysis and interviews. We used a triangulation of data with the aim of understanding generational diversity at the ONDA by studying it from more than one perspective (Pourtois and Desmet, 1988).

The first step of our research consisted of an observational field study. This choice is explained by the absence of a common theoretical framework that makes it possible to describe and understand how to manage intergenerational conflicts in a company. The interaction with the actors helped us to identify deep representations of the phenomenon. The observation was made "in real time". The second stage of this research focused on the analysis of documents and publications describing the characteristics of each generation. This step allowed us to acquire "such a complete vision of the problem" (Evrard et al, 2009). However, semi-structured interviews are our main source of data.

We conducted 24 interviews, seeking the greatest possible diversity of interviewees. The semantic saturation threshold was reached in the 20th interview, the four subsequent interviews did not provide more information. Previously, we developed an interview guide based on the literature. This interview guide has been constructed in a uniform manner so that questions can be asked, at the same time, to both professional, managerial staff, and human resources professionals. It is made up of two parts: The first one aimed at determining the characteristics and expectations of each generation, the second one is devoted to the types of generational conflicts within the company. Two types of interviews were retained. A first series of six semi-structured interviews was conducted with the company's executives and HR managers. They focused on the characteristics and expectations of Generation Z and intergenerational conflicts following the advent of this new generation.

A second series of semi-structured interviews was conducted with eighteen collaborators about generational diversity within ONDA.

We selected people with different profiles and generations. The diversity of the profiles and generations of the informants as well as the functions they occupy seem to give more relevance and validity to the comments collected. The interviews lasted an average of 45 minutes. They were recorded through a tape recorder and then transcribed. The transcription allowed us to get a corpus of 24 testimonies.

Table 3 summarizes the characteristics of our sample, so we chose NVIVO software which was relevant for thematic data analysis.

2.3.3. Description of the sample

We opted for semi-structured, multi-stakeholder interviews in order to diversify opinions and points of view. Since Generation Z is a concept that concerns several actors, the population interviewed was drawn from various profiles and generations to reinforce the internal validity of the study and ensure the representativeness of our sample in the sense of Campbell and Stanley (1966). The people interviewed are all from the airline industry.

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

Table 3: Detailed characteristics of the qualitative study sample :

code	professions	Age	Gender	Diploma
001	Director of Operations	58	male	Master's degree
002	Head of HR division	57	male	Master's degree
003	Head of skills maintenance	40	male	Master's degree
004	Head of Quality Division	44	female	Bachelor's degree
005	Head of coordination division	51	female	Bachelor's degree
006	engineer	36	male	Master's degree
007	Air traffic controller	55	male	Master's degree
008	Air traffic controller	46	male	Master's degree
009	Air traffic controller	44	female	Master's degree
010	Air traffic controller	39	male	Master's degree
011	Air traffic controller	37	male	Master's degree
012	Air traffic controller	24	female	Master's degree
013	Air safety technician	28	male	Bachelor's degree
014	Firefighter	32	male	Bac + 2
015	Air safety technician	26	male	Bachelor's degree
016	Air safety technician	25	female	Bachelor's degree
017	Firefighter	38	male	Bac + 2
018	instructor	47	male	Master's degree
019	engineer	42	male	Master's degree
020	Trainee	24	female	Master's degree
021	Executive HR staff	31	female	Bac + 2
022	Accounting	52	male	Master's degree
023	Electronics	36	male	Master's degree
024	Hostess reception	23	female	Bac + 2

Table. 4: Overall description of the sample.

Job	Number
Managers	1
HRD/HRR	1
Executive employees	3
Air traffic controllers	6
Air safety technician	2
Professional and managerial staff representatives	3
Executive HR staff	4
Firefighter	2
Trainee	1
Instructor	1
Total	24

3. Results of the qualitative study: content analysis

After presenting the context of the work on Generation Z, as well as the methodology used for our research, we will now proceed to the presentation and discussion of the results we obtained following the administration of our interview guide to ONDA employees in Morocco.

The results make it possible to identify the impact of the arrival of Generation Z on intergenerational relations and the way in which they are applied within ONDA according to the vision of the interviewees.

The company studied (ONDA) has specific characteristics in terms of the distribution of generations. In fact, four generations live together in this company. The baby boomers represent 13.03% of the total ONDA workforce, generation X represents 32.21% of the total workforce, generation Y is the most dominant with 49.30% of the workforce and finally the new generation Z which represents only 5.45% of the total workforce.

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

In this company, we have noticed that the management of the new generations has its own peculiarities. Young Y and Z have another relationship to time, organization and authority. We have had the opportunity to notice that the modes of operation and the aspirations are different, sometimes contradictory.

According to the interviews carried out:

- For Baby Boomers, respect is synonymous with politeness, punctuality and respect for the statutes and the organization in place "Not being on time means not respecting colleagues who are always on time "said a 55-year-old air traffic controller.
- For Generation X, respect is synonymous with respect for the contract and fairness: "Not doing what you promise is a sign of disrespect that calls into question trust and commitment. Adds a 47-year-old trainer.
- From the point of view of Generation Y, respect is synonymous with parity, a place given in daily operations. "Not being treated as an equal with other team members is a sign of disrespect," says a 38-year-old firefighter.
- The majority of the Generation Z staff interviewed stated that the main actor in recognition remains the close manager, which they encounter every day. They are looking for benevolent behavior on the part of their hierarchy and seek management based on trust (possibility of adapting work schedules, occasional practice of teleworking, obtaining solidarity leave, etc.). According to the HR manager, the young generation Z is shaking up the habits of managers and HR, they have a flexible pace and change the rules of the game in the company. They cannot bear to be accountable to a superior, moreover this term is completely hostile to them, it would be better to set their objectives and let them do it for themselves. You have to constantly challenge them so as not to bore them.
- Generation Z seems to expect clear objectives and regular "feedback" from their hierarchy. Results should ideally be accompanied by financial recognition, once the objectives have been achieved. For this, the challenges must be real, leaving them free to act and create. Autonomy in the face of action seems to be a powerful lever to mobilize Generation Z, which wants to be above all independent and innovative, with a strong expectation of self-fulfillment.

We have previously seen that each generation has its own expectations and aspirations, which constitutes an additional level of complexity for managers.

Consider the question: "Faced with the diversity of generations, how can organizations promote intergenerational cooperation? ", Leads to thinking about the concrete aspects of the collaborative approach which makes it possible to achieve collective performance by meeting the following five objectives.

- 1- Develop a shared vision of how the team should operate based on a charter of values and behaviors.
- 2- Federate the different generations on common objectives promoting cooperation, mutual aid and the sharing of knowledge.
- 3- Create the conditions for group work enabling the different generations to make their differences truly complementary.
- 4- Detect and deal fairly with conflicts that may arise between different age groups.
- 5- Foster exchange opportunities that generate collaborative work and implementation involving different generations.

Conclusion

Faced with the permanent professional context relating to innovation, human resources management is more than ever confronted with a "war for talent" with regard to young recruits. Thus, to attract and retain the talents of Generation Z, it becomes necessary to understand their expectations, attitudes at work and values.

In view of the observations made throughout our study, the fact remains that the arrival of Generation Z will have a major impact on the world of work, and this will further disrupt the habits of previous generations and managers in the future.

These young people of generation Z, who will be the managers of tomorrow, will be confronted in such a short period of time with a new generation of alphas (α) which will be more than ever Web 3.0 or Web 4.0, Fog,

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

Cloud oriented and where the idea of the workplace may disappear and give way to that of telework or collective hub.

The great challenge of intergenerationality is an exciting project to be lived in the service of collective intelligence, it offers many possibilities in the field of creation and innovation. It is indeed in this particular field that the competitiveness of companies is at stake today.

Bibliographical references

- 1- ALLAIN, Carol (2005). *Génération Y: L'enfant roi devenu adulte*, Laval, Logique Inc., 175 p.
- 2- AUDET, Michel (2004). «La gestion de la relève et le choc des générations», *Gestion*, vol. 29, no. 3, p. 20-26.
- 3- ARSENAULT P. (2004), "Validating generational differences: a legitimate diversity and leadership issue", *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, Vol. 25, n°1 et 2, p.125-141.
- 4- A. Kingston, *Get ready for Generation Z*, MACLEANS, 2014.
- 5- ATTISA-DONFUT (1988), *Sociologie des générations : l'empreinte du temps*, Presses Universitaires de France, Paris.
- 6- Becton, J.B., Walker, H.J., Farmer, A.J. Generational Differences in Workplace Behavior. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*. 2014; 44 (3): 175-189.
- 7- Beutell, N.J., Wittig-Berman, U. Work-Family Conflict and Work-Family Synergy for Generation X, Baby Boomers, And Matures: Generational Differences, Predictors, and Satisfaction Outcomes. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*. 2008; 23 (5): 507-523.
- 8- Bartley, S.J., Ladd, P.G., Morris, M.L. (2007). Managing the multigenerational workplace: answers for managers and trainers. *CUPA-HR Journal*, 28-34.
- 9- Boudreau, D. J. (2006). *Les courants générationnels et leurs tendances. Quelle disposition adopter ?*
- 10-Dalmas, M. (2014). Quelles valeurs organisationnelles pour la génération Y ?, *Revue Management et Avenir*, 72, 113-132.
- 11-DALMAS M. (2008), *L'incidence des valeurs individuelles sur la motivation et l'implication organisationnelle, pour des cadres en ressources humaines*, Thèse en Sciences de Gestion, Université de Toulouse 1.
- 12-Dalmas, M. (2017). Une génération Z en quête de sens, *The Conversation*.
- 13-Dalmas, M. (2017). Génération Y et attitude d'autodétermination ?, *RIPCO*, 22 (12), 83-102.
- 14-Douglas, M., Howell, T., Nelson, E., Pilkington, L., & Salinas, I. (2015). Improve the function of multigenerational teams. *Nursing Management*, 46, 11–13. doi:10.1097/01.NUMA.0000459098.71482.c4.
- 15-Deci, E.L., Ryan, R.M. (1985). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behaviour*, New York, NY: Plenum Press.
- 16-Dejoux C, Wechtler H. *Diversité générationnelle : implications, principes et outils de management. Management et Avenir*. 2011/3(43).
- 17-Durkin, D. (2006). Managing the new generation, *Business NH Magazine*, 23(8), 21-22.
- 18-Durkin, D. (2007a). Engaging four generations to enhance productivity, *Chief Learning Officer*, 6(3), 30-35.
- 19-Eisner, S. P., (2005).Managing generation Y. *SAM Advanced Management Journal*. 2005; 70 (4): 4–15.
- 20-GUENOT Frédérique, « Génération Z : pas encore dans l'entreprise, elle inquiète déjà », *Focus RH*, 04/10/2016 [en ligne] <http://www.focusrh.com/strategie-rh/mobilite-interne-fidelisation-des-salaries/generation-z-pas-encore-dans-l-entreprise-elle-inquiete-deja-29040.html>
- 21-Igalens, J., Roussel, P. (1998).*Méthodes de recherche en gestion des ressources humaines*, Edition Economica: Paris.
- 22-Iogulescu, M.C. (2016). Generation Z and its perception of work, *Cross cultural management journal*, 18(9).
- 23-J. Gibson and Al., *Generation Z ascending*, 2013.
- 24-KUPPERSCHMIDT B. (2000), "Multigeneration employee: strategies for effective management", *Health Care Manager*, Vol. 19, n°1, p. 65-76.
- 25-Mead M. 1971), *Le Fossé des générations traduit de l'américain par Jean Clairevoye Paris*,
- 26-Mead M. *Le fossé des générations : les nouvelles relations dans les années 1970. Paris: Denoel Gonthier ; 1979. UETE.*
- 27-Mannheim K. *Das Problem der Generationen. 2e ed. Berlin : Wissensoziologie, Neuwied Luchterhand ; 1964. (1re édition: 1928).*

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

- 28-Micoleta, J. Generation Z Teens Stereotyped as 'Lazy and Unaware'. Accepted and posted with Number 2012. Available: <http://www.huffingtonpost.com/>
- 29-Mitchell, D.A. Generation Z: Striking the Balance: Healthy Doctors for a Healthy Community. Australian Family Physician. 2008; 37(8): 665-672.
- 30-N. Baker, *La génération Z un raz de marée dans l'entreprise*, Tribune Verte, 2016, num. 2780.
- 31-PICHAULT F. et PLEYERS M. (2010), « Pour en finir avec la génération Y... Enquête sur une représentation managériale », *congrès de l'A.G.R.H*, Saint-Malo, 43 p.
- 32-PRALONG J. (2008), « La generation Y au travail : un peril jeune ? », *Rouen Business school*, Département Management et Stratégie, 22 p.
- 33-PETIT, Mélaïne (2008). *Les attentes professionnelles des jeunes de la génération Y*, Rapport no 1 : Recension des écrits, Montréal, HEC Montréal, 71p.
- 34-Peterson, H. Millennials Are Old News – Here's Everything You Should Know about Generation Z. Accepted and posted with Number 2014. Available: <http://www.businessinsider.com/>
- 35-RAPPIN B. (2016), « Actualité de la génération Y et ses implications pour la gestion », *Revue Internationale de Psychosociologie et de Gestion des Comportements Organisationnels*, vol.23, N°53, p.23-27.
- 36-Salahuddin, M. M., (2010). Generational Differences Impact on Leadership Style and Organizational Success. *Journal of Diversity Management*. 2010; 5 (2): 1-6.
- 37-SCHEIN E.-H. (1978), *Career dynamics: matching individual and organizational needs*, Reading: Addison-Wesley.
- 38-SCHEIN E.-H. (1990), *Career Anchors: discovering your real values*, Ed. Pfeiffer and Company, San Diego (California).
- 39-Tulgan B. *Generation X: slackers? Or the workforce of the future? Employment Relations Today*. 1997;24(2):55-64..
- 40-ZEMKE, Ron, Claire RAINES, et Bob FILIPCZAK (2000). *Generations at Work: Managing the Clash of Veterans, Boomers, Xers and Nexters in your Workplace*, AMACOM, 280 p.